

**TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL SPHERES IN AMITAV GHOSH'S *THE SHADOW LINES*:
MAPPING THE HISTORICAL NARRATIVES**

Mr. Maharshi Vyas

Research Scholar, Sadguru Mahila College, Affiliated to Saurashtra University,

Rajkot, Gujarat. Email: maharshivyas009@gmail.com

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Abstract

*The researcher aims to analyse Amitav Ghosh's *The Shadow Lines* with special reference of temporal and spatial spheres with the consideration of historical narratives. Ghosh's fondness for mapping events with an actual source through the documentation of the same with a view to strengthen the historical narratives in the light of temporal and spatial horizons are apparent in *The Shadow Lines*. The researcher has explored the above-mentioned concerns and has expounded the study of the novel with the prime consideration of the shifts in temporal and spatial dynamics. Ghosh's construction of historical narratives and mapping the real incidents with the subsequent chain of other events which adhere the diverse dimensions of time and space in the novel has been analysed by the researcher in the proposed study.*

*The historical narratives of the 1964 Calcutta riots, clash of Germany and Britain in World War 2 and the aftermath effects have been primarily focused by the researcher with the temporal and spatial dynamics. The historical narrative of the political upheaval between Calcutta and Dhaka have been analysed in the temporal and spatial realm along with Ghosh's use of documenting the actual sources prevalent at that particular time period: newspaper headlines, short reports and radio commentary. In *The Shadow Lines* Ghosh's use of mapping the events from Mrs. Price family's picture of photograph has been compared with Agha Shahid Ali's use of postcard in the poem *Postcard from Kashmir* as well as the Oriental binary of Western and Eastern tradition through the characters of Ila, Tridib and Tha'mma have at minor focus.*

Keywords: *Temporal, Spatial, Historical Narrative, Mapping, Documentation, Ghosh, Political violence*

Amitav Ghosh is an Indian-English writer, he has gained popularity with *The Shadow Lines* (1988) one of his earliest ventures in writing. *The Shadow Lines* is a novel, which represents profound historical narratives. Ghosh's art lies in recreation of history along with

“Time” and “Space”, he reframes historical narratives with the techniques of memorization and mapping events to create meaningful narratives. *The Shadow Lines* revolves around the “Temporal” and “Spatial” historical constructions, in which ‘temporal’ denotes ‘time’ of events whereas, ‘spatial’ denotes ‘space’ or physical location of events. Ghosh’s mastery in citing the real historic events with the technique of ‘Mapping’ which refers to the use of timelines, mind maps or linkage of chain of events in order to better understand the narrative, which has played crucial part in the novel. “...Artistic texts usually present the temporal-spatial picture of the world from a symbolical metaphorical aspect. Regardless of its literary genre, fiction text describes events, phenomena, or mental activity of a person in their temporal and spatial orientation ...” (Havrylenko-Rusak 112) *The Shadow Lines* presents unnamed narrator’s orientation about the temporal and spatial aspects about historical incidents and witnessing its well-documentations. The unnamed narrator of the novel is nothing but the mouthpiece of Ghosh in mapping the historic events through the memorizations, it’s as though, Ghosh himself has narrated and weaved the historical narratives directly to the readers. Ghosh’s representation of the historical events is for the search of identity, which had suppressed under the weight of imaginary geographical borders created by people in their mind, “... that carried one beyond the limits of one’s mind to other times and other places, and even, if one was lucky, to a place where there was no border between oneself and one’s image in the mirror.” (Ghosh 32) from this quote the inference can be drawn; the failure of homogenous national identity which has been reflected in the novel through the political struggle of Dhaka and Calcutta largely because of the religious tracts of the Hazratbal Relic which had been disappeared from its origin at Srinagar, Kashmir. Thus, the communal violence occurred and influenced from the religious affairs.

Ghosh’s fondness with the temporal and spatial aspects are apparent in *The Shadow Lines*. The aspects of time and space; both are interconnected with History or in other words, we often link historical accounts of events with time and space. With the opening line of the novel Ghosh takes us to the time of World War 2, “In 1939, thirteen years before I was born ...” (Ghosh 3) Ghosh has majorly focussed on the three places in *The Shadow Lines*: London, Calcutta and Dhaka, these places are at the core in representing spatial aspects which were well taken into the consideration through the places and the characters of the novel, we may also make the distinction between Eastern and Western culture depicted in the novel. For example, Ila’s character is westernized and she wants freedom of living and for that she adopts Western

tradition, which has reflected in her choice of language, her style of wearing cloths and rejection of Indian values, she had suffered after her marriage to the non-Indian man and eventually she got divorce. On the other hand, through the character of Tridib (narrator's uncle) and Tha'mma (narrator's grandmother) we find Indianness in every aspect of their life through the Indian culture. Both represents patriotism and Indian belief: we are one Rashtra culturally. Tridib's selflessness and the national sprit is constant and ends with his death in the riots. Postcolonial critic Edward Said's *Orientalism* also can be taken into the account for further research, drawing upon the *oriental* binaries.

The initial part of the novel depicts the struggle of World War 2 with the continuous strife between Britain and Germany, the bombing and air strike raids and its aftermath are portrayed by Ghosh with the constant shift in the places, although the time period of the events were same, this spatial shift gives edge to the readers to imagine the circumstances of the events and its actualization with the real historical accounts, however, at the same time it also challenges readers with the quick shifts in spatial and temporal complexities. *The Shadow Lines* presents the unnamed narrator and *his* fondness for his uncle Tridib; he religiously followed him and always wanted to be like him. Tridib always lives in the imagination world and he takes the narrator as well as the readers into the time of 1940 England, where due to World War 2 Germany had attacked England with bombing and as an aftermath the destruction of most of the houses, streets and grounds. Ghosh has provided every minute details like the road and street names, address, affected parts of the houses and buildings with their structural conditions which were happened as a consequence of bombing. These portrayals throw light to Ghosh's art of memorisation and mapping the chain of events with then ongoing events through unnamed narrator. One such instance of mapping: "...on the corner of Lymington Road, I know what it's called: it's called Lymington Mansions, and an incendiary bomb fell on it, and burned down two floors. That was on the 1st of October 1940, two days before your uncle died." (Ghosh 61) the minuteness of the incident with precision of time and space are evident in the above-mentioned citation; where the spatial aspects such as name of the road and area "Lymington Mansions", affected parts of it "two floors" and the temporal aspects such the exact time of the incident, "1st October, 1940" mapping with the timeline of the death of the uncle; hence linking it with another spatial sphere. These temporal and spatial narratives are nothing but the products of Ghosh's memorisation power to depict the events with interconnectedness of time and place.

In *The Shadow Lines* Ghosh has used the picture of photograph of a family which were became the victims of the bombing in World War 2, with a view to mapping the chain of events Ghosh has portrayed the family picture photograph of Mrs. Price's family and with the art of imagination and on the basis of the evidences, he has made an effort to connect the aftermath destruction of the building with the family photograph of Mrs. Price's family which had been just taken before the bombing. This gives the sense of nostalgia and similarities can be drawn with the Indian diasporic poet Agha Shahid Ali's poem *Postcard from Kashmir* which have been celebrated for its nostalgic appeal for poet's homeland India. "Kashmir shrinks into my mailbox, / my home a neat four by six inches." (Ali 1-2) Agha Shahid Ali's nostalgia for Kashmir through the postcard "photograph" of his homeland Kashmir which has symbolized the childhood memorization of the poet. The symbolism of shrinking Kashmir to his mailbox can be interpreted as his memorization and nostalgia of his homeland which still has place in his memory. Ghosh has also given vivid portrayal of the aftermaths of the German's bombing on the London streets through the photograph picture of the affected family like Agha Shahid Ali's use of postcard to express his feelings. Ghosh has portrayed the narrative based on the photograph:

The stairs were the first part of the house to collapse. The wood gave a long, wrenching groan when the blast shook the foundations. That momentary pause gave Tresawsen time to push Mike clear of the stairs and throw his body over Francesca's. Then a beam fell upon him, killing him instantly, breaking his spine. (Ghosh 113)

The actualizations of the incident can only be attained by the presence on the time of the incident and its immensely difficult task to link the subsequent formations of the event, however, Ghosh's use of mapping and memorization made it possible to justified the incident, 'justify' might be correct word rather than choosing the word 'perception'.

The communal conflicts between Calcutta and Dhaka are at the central core of the novel which forms the broader part of *The Shadow Lines*. The constant spatial shift between Calcutta and Dhaka, with the immobile temporal aspect which enriches the depths of the communal struggle of 1964 as depicted in *The Shadow Lines*. Ghosh remarks, "Every word I write about those events of 1964 is the product of a struggle with silence ..." (Ghosh 240) through the character of Tha'mma, whose family lived in Dhaka and she herself lived there in her earlier years; Ghosh has represented the complexities of the changing the dynamics of the 'place',

Dhaka after the communal riots had taken place. Through the nostalgia of Tha'mma, who were constantly questions every aspect of Dhaka with the repetition of "But where's Dhaka?" (Ghosh 227) this statement indicates the nostalgic struggle to regained the memorization of the place which were once a homeland and due to the communal violence, riots and partition the natives were force to leave the same land. The descriptions of the Dhaka and its streets, bazar, houses, etc. after the temporal shift of the communal disharmony which had completely violated the memory of the same place and also it had caused the loss of identity in the people who once lived there, especially Tha'mma, who was suffered from the temporal and spatial spheres and unbale to regain the memory of her homeland, thus, she lived in a fragmented imaginations.

Meenakshi Mukherjee in her essay *Mapps and Mirrors: Coordinates of Meaning in The Shadow Lines* has remarked, "... one of the many intricate patterns that weaves the novel together is the coalescing of time and space in a seamless continuity, memory endowing remembered places with solidity, and imagination the recounted ones ..." (Mukherjee 256-257) in *The Shadow Lines* Ghosh's use of reframing historical narrative relocates the historical incidents under the realm of time and space with the continuity of mapping those incidents with the aid of popular sources of the common people; Ghosh has given the actual documentation of different sources: newspaper, radio commentary and news reports, which were prevalent at different temporal horizons and it also add the firmness to the historical narratives and thus, mapping the events with the subsequent chain of events in which the accuracy of the real documentation has preserved. For instance, "... newspaper section ...volume for January and February, 1964 ...headline which said: *Madras Test Begins Today*." (Ghosh 245) while narrating the historical constructions of the 1964 riots in the novel; Ghosh has linked this event with another event of the "test match" which were commencing on that same timeframe as the riots were taking place. Hence, strengthening spatial aspects of the one particular event, which revolves around the one still temporal ground of the history.

Newspaper headlines and short reports were crucial in the mapping process of subsequent historical incidents in *The Shadow Lines*, some of the instances from the novel have been cited by the researcher in order to furnish the proposed argument: "... It was the section on the war of 1962... it was the section on the 1965 war with Pakistan." (Ghosh 245) Ghosh has also represented the temporal-spatial narratives on India-China war in 1962 and how China had taken the Himalayan heights and Tha'mma as a witness of India-Pakistan war in 1965

through listening the news via radio commentary. Through the unnamed narrator, Ghosh has weaved documentation of different newspaper headlines especially of the crisis of 1964 Calcutta riots; "...a short report... headline which said: *Twenty-nine killed in riots.*" (Ghosh 246) the precision of mapping the actual events in the narrative construction of the novel creates the sense of belongingness to time and space portrayed by Ghosh in the novel. "...I turned the pages to the edition of Saturday, 11 January 1964, and sure enough, there it was: a huge banner headline which said: Curfew in Calcutta, Police Open Fire, 10 dead, 15 wounded." (Ghosh 247) this above-cited lines of the novel showcases Ghosh's fondness towards the minute depictions; for instance, he has provided the exact date and month of the one particular incident, we often observe that in majority of the time writers only mentions 'year' of the event to support their argument unless there were any significance of the particular day and month, however, in these terms the accurateness of Ghosh is throughout *The Shadow Lines*.

Elleke Boehmer in the book *Colonial and Postcolonial Literature* has stated, "... More freely perhaps in a historical fiction than in a conventional history, a disappearing, threatened, or neglected way of life could be re-created and preserved ..." (Boehmer 188) Ghosh's *The Shadow Lines* depicts the threatened lives of the people from diverse arena of time and space, through the historical narrative he has aimed to recreate history with the fiction. "The lead story had nothing to do with riots of any kind nor with Calcutta: It was about the sixty-eight session of the Congress Party in Bhubaneswar ..." (Ghosh 246) drawing upon the spatial aspect Ghosh has provided the reference of politics and the political party simultaneously with the ongoing communal struggle of 1964 riots, this construction of historical narrative in *The Shadow Lines* has not solely depended on any one particular incident which were at the centre of wheel but the rich diversity of events have been mapped by Ghosh under the realm of time and space.

Dipesh Chakrabarty in *Provincializing Europe* delves deep in the concept of historicism, he remarks, "A critique of historicism therefore goes to the heart of the question of political modernity in non-Western societies ..." (Chakrabarty 9) *The Shadow Lines* presents the historical narrative of the political turmoil between Calcutta and Dhaka which are at the heart of the novel along with Germany and Britain's political stance in World War 2. The India-China war in 1962, the Calcutta riots of 1964, the India-Pakistan war in 1965 and the independence of Bangladesh served as what Dipesh Chakrabarty has remarked, "non-Western societies" (Chakrabarty 9) India, Pakistan and then newly independent Bangladesh and their

political struggle forms the appraisal of historicism in the novel. The constant political and religious struggle between Calcutta and Dhaka, especially for the borders which were "... separated by time and space – history and geography ..." (Bose 19) and the so called borders which were at the centre for the people were imaginary, it was nothing but the "shadow lines" drawn by the people for the sake of their inner satisfactions and which had been classified by the heterogenous religious tracts before the newly independent East-Pakistan named as Bangladesh. "...East Pakistan were now in the grip of a 'frenzy' of looting, killing and burning." (Ghosh 252) the killings of one's own people are by no means an ordinary incident but the result of unreal borders or shadow lines which had been created by the people themselves.

To conclude, historical narratives of Germany-Britain World War 2, 1964 Calcutta riots, political upheaval, communal disharmony, and its aftermath effects in Ghosh's *The Shadow Lines* have been analysed under the temporal and spatial spheres. Ghosh's precision in documenting real sources of the historical incidents in order to build up the historical narratives in the novel which constructs the dynamics of time and space of the events, these have also been taken into the account by the researcher. Ghosh's unique style of constructing historical narratives with the temporal and spatial spheres especially with documenting events with the aid of newspapers, reports and radio commentary has also been utilized to analyse the proposed study. The spectrum of historical incidents forms the base for the human quest: search for identity. In general terms, the notion of people in which they create illusional borders in all aspects of life; which causes the communal and political violence, however, in reality it's just shadow lines.

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